

Preparation and Properties of Zirconium Sulphosalicylic Acid Jellies.

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Berkmann and Zocher (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, **42**, 309, 322), Wo. Ostwald and Mertens (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1926, **23**, 242) and others have made detailed investigations of the properties of mercury derivatives of sulphosalicylic acid which are known to form colloidal suspensions in water and which exhibit marked anisotropy, and double refraction. The author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 367) has also studied the conditions of formation of the jellies of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid. Recently, the author has succeeded in preparing the jellies of zirconium sulphosalicylic acid for the first time and in the present communication, an account will be given of the conditions of the formation of this jelly.

Even in dilute solutions, zirconium oxychloride forms a stable solution and it does not develop any opalescence when kept for a long time. However, if its dilute solution be boiled and allowed to dialyse, it hydrolyses and gives a transparent sol of zirconium hydroxide. When a concentrated solution of zirconium oxychloride is mixed with a concentrated solution of sulphosalicylic acid, it forms a colourless mixture. Now, if to this transparent mixture be added water to a certain dilution, opalescence at once develops, and finally, the whole of the solution becomes completely opaque. After some time, a precipitate also appears, which settles down, leaving a clear supernatant liquid. The author has found that by careful regulation of the concentrations of zirconium oxychloride, sulphosalicylic acid and water, not only stable colloidal sol of zirconium sulphosalicylic acid is obtained, but very transparent glass-like hard jellies can also be prepared.

In the following experiments, a 50 % solution of 5-sulphosalicylic acid, $C_6H_3SO_3H \cdot OH \cdot COOH$, $2H_2O$, (3.99N), was used which was free from sulphate ions. An almost saturated solution of zirconium oxychloride, $ZrOCl_2$, corresponding to 310.68 g. ZrO_2 per litre was found to be very suitable for jelly formation. The time of

setting and the nature of the jellies obtained at different concentrations are given in the following tables. The jelly forming components were thoroughly mixed in test tubes which were allowed to stand for a number of days.

TABLE I.

Amount of zirconium oxychloride soln. used each time = 1 c.c.

Amount of sulphosalicylic acid.	Amount of water.	Time of setting and the nature of the jelly.
0.5 c.c.	0 c.c.	Clear solution, no jelly even in 4 days
0.5	0.5	do do do
0.5	1.0	do do do
0.5	1.5	Transparent jelly in 85 hrs.
0.5	2.0	Transparent jelly in 72 hrs.
0.5	2.5	Transparent jelly in 50 hrs.
1.5	0	Slight precipitate but no jelly
1.5	0.5	No jelly within 4 days
1.5	1.0	Transparent jelly within 60 hrs.
1.5	1.5	Transparent jelly with slight opalescence in 40 hrs.
1.5	2.0	Opalescent jelly in 30 hrs.
2.0	0	Transparent jelly in 78 hrs.
2.0	0.5	Transparent jelly in 46 hrs.
2.0	1.0	Transparent jelly in 46 hrs.
2.0	1.5	Opalescent jelly in 40 hrs.
2.0	2.0	Translucent jelly in 19 hrs.
2.0	3.0	Translucent jelly in 10 hrs.

From the results recorded in the above table, it would be seen that (i) the greater the amount of water added to a particular mixture of zirconium oxychloride and sulphosalicylic acid, the less is the setting time of the jelly, but the jelly is more opalescent, (ii) the jellies obtained with the same amount of zirconium oxychloride and water but with varying concentrations of sulphosalicylic acid show that an increase in the concentration of sulphosalicylic acid causes also a decrease in the time of setting. It is a general rule, that where a jelly has a marked tendency of developing opalescence, the time of the setting of the jelly is less and the speed of development of turbidity is more rapid. Even the jellies which have only a slight opalescence at the time of setting become almost opaque if kept for a large number of days.

In a previous publication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 193) the author has studied the influence of temperature on the setting of numerous inorganic jellies and also mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid jelly. The influence of temperature is also very much marked in the case of zirconium sulphosalicylic acid jelly. In the following table, the results are recorded concerning the setting of a jelly prepared by the addition of 1 c. c. of zirconium oxychloride solution to 2 c. c. of sulphosalicylic acid and 2 c. c. of water. The contents were allowed to set in baths maintained at different temperatures.

TABLE II.

Temperature.	Time of setting.	Nature of the jelly.
80°	1 min.	Opaque
70°	2	Opaque with slight light transmission
60°	11	Translucent at the time of setting but becoming opaque just after a few minutes
55°	22	Translucent jelly
50°	35	Translucent jelly
45°	75	Translucent jelly
40°	240	Transparent with slight opalescence
30°	19 hrs.	Transparent with very slight opalescence

Thus zirconium sulphosalicylic acid jelly is more readily obtained at a higher temperature, but the texture and fineness of the jelly are markedly spoiled.

Some of the best jellies of zirconium sulphosalicylic acid are as transparent as mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid jellies, but on ageing they become comparatively harder than the mercuri-ones. These zirconium jellies do not undergo any syneresis, but on drying exhibit a peculiar sort of rupture with beautiful pattern of cracks. This is due to the high concentration of the jelly which yields a hard compactness. Mercuri-jellies are obtained at comparatively low concentrations. If the jelly producing solutions of zirconium jelly are allowed to set at a high temperature, an opaque mass is obtained; but if a transparent jelly set at ordinary temperature and kept for a sufficient number of days be now transferred to a bath maintained at a high temperature, the opalescence is not so rapidly

developed. In this respect the jelly is quite resisting to the temperature.

The influence of some ions on the setting of the jelly has also been investigated. The following table shows the influence of potassium chloride and ammonium sulphate.

TABLE III.

Zirconium oxychloride solution used = 1 c. c. Sulphosalicylic acid added = 2 c. c. Total volume kept = 5 c. c. by adding water.

N-KCl in c. c.	0	0.5	1.0	1.5	
Time of setting in hrs.	19	26	27	29	
N/5-Ammonium sulphate in c.c.	0	0.3	0.7	1.1	1.5
Time of setting in hrs.	19	14	10.25	0	Precipitate appearing in $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. but setting to a solid mass in $6\frac{1}{2}$ hrs.

Thus it would be seen, that in presence of monovalent ions, like chlorine from potassium chloride, the sol of zirconium sulphosalicylic acid is markedly stabilised. Similar stabilisation is observed in the case of aluminium nitrate. In the presence of ammonium sulphate or any sulphate, the coagulation is rapid and a jelly is obtained in a comparatively less time. The jellies obtained in the presence of sulphate ions are more opaque too. The sensitising influence of citrate ions is all the more marked and in presence of even very small concentrations of sodium citrate, only precipitated masses are obtained and not the true jelly. From all these facts, it is clear that zirconium sulphosalicylic acid forms a positively charged sol. Being a very impure system, the coagulating effect of chloride ions is masked by the protecting action of highly adsorbed potassium ions from potassium chloride, and hence a stabilisation is observed when the jelly is allowed to set in its presence. An abnormal dilution effect will also be observed in this case, *i.e.*, if coagulation be effected by potassium chloride, the dilute sol would be found more stable than the concentrated sol. With sulphate and citrate ions, normal effects will be observed.

In many respects, the zirconium sulphosalicylic acid differs from mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid. The latter forms a negatively charged sol, whilst the former is a positively charged one. Zirconium sols and gels when evaporated to dryness do not pass into the colloidal state again when water is added. In this respect they are heat-irreversible. Mercuri- acid forms a typical organic jelly which exhibits a sort of

'melting' at a higher temperature, and takes more time to set when the temperature is raised. As has just been shown, the case with zirconium jelly is just the reverse of it.

Wo. Ostwald and Mertens (*loc. cit.*) observed the 'dissolving' influence of Cl^- , Br^- , CN^- , CNS^- ions on the colloidal phase of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid. In presence of these ions, the colloidal nature of the sol at once disappears. However, in the case of zirconium sulphosalicylic acid, no such behaviour is observed.

The jelly of zirconium sulphosalicylic acid is only produced when sulphosalicylic acid is used and not when its neutral sodium salt. The medium must be highly acidic in order to produce a fine jelly. In the following table, the influence of alkali on the formation of this jelly has been illustrated.

TABLE IV.

Zirconium oxychloride = 1 c.c. Sulphosalicylic acid = 2 c.c.
Total volume = 5 c.c.

NaOH (N-6.84).	Time of setting.	Nature of the jelly.
0.2 c. c.	7 hrs. 40 mins.	Translucent
0.3	6 hrs.	Translucent
0.4	4 hrs.	Translucent
0.5	1 hr. 50 mins	Very opalescent
0.55	1 hr. 15 mins.	Opaque
0.6	1 min.	Opaque

Thus it would be seen that no jelly can be obtained in neutral or alkaline medium. It appears that zirconium sulphosalicylic acid is peptised to the colloidal form by the adsorption of hydrogen ions from the system. Sulphosalicylic acid is a fairly strong acid with a sufficiently high dissociation constant and so in strongly acidic solutions, only a very small part of zirconium sulphosalicylate may be supposed to be in equilibrium with zirconium hydroxide formed by hydrolysis.

Zirconium sulphosalicylic acid may be taken to possess one of the following structures :

Further work on this substance is in progress.

